

Self-Concept of Senior Secondary School Students in relation to their Gender and Types of Management of School in Sivasagar District Assam

Abstract: Self-concept is a part of personality as review of building concept for the self. Personality is the total configuration of characteristics; ways of feelings, thinking, and behaving that comprise the individual's unique method of adapting and reacting to his environment. Self-concept in adolescent influences their development of personality. The objective of the study is- to study the level of self-concept of senior secondary school students and to analyze whether there is significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district of Assam in relation to gender and types of management of school. In the present study a representative sample of 100 senior secondary school students from Sivasagar district are selected. Out of the 100 sample, 50 male and 50 female are both from govt. and private school under Assam Higher Secondary Education Council. In the present study self-concept questionnaire was developed and standardized by R.K. Saraswat (2024) and personal datasheet (self-developed) was used. The result revealed that highest percentage of students has average level of self-concept. It also showed that there is no significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district of Assam in relation to gender and types of management of school.

Ms. Piku Doley¹, Prof. Babita Choudhury²

Affiliation

¹Research Scholar, Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya, Nagaon, Assam, India.

²Research Supervisor, Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankaradeva Viswavidyalaya, Nagaon, Assam, India

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Introduction

Self-concept

Generally self means the conscious reflection of one's own being or identity, as an object separate from others or from the environment. Self-concept is a part of personality as review of building concept for the self. Personality is the total configuration of characteristics; ways of feelings, thinking, and behaving that comprise the individual's unique method of adapting and reacting to his environment. Self-concept in adolescent influences their development of personality.

William James (1890) in his first introductory textbook in Psychology described the self as the way in which the self could be expanded to include one's cloths, one's home and one's society. Self encompasses both the "I" and "Me" that are both the subject and the object

of the experience, both the knower and the known. Self-concept is unique, dynamic, and always evolving with individual's interaction with the physical and social world.

"Self-concept is the cognitive or thinking aspect of self (related to one's self-image) and generally refers to the totality of a complex, organized, and dynamic system of learned beliefs, attitudes and opinions that each person holds to be true about his or her personal existence" (Purkey, 1988).

Self-concept can be understood as the relatively stable picture people have of themselves and their own attributes (International encyclopedia of education).

"Self-concept is more of a collection of selves rather than a static thing. It includes hundreds of self-perceptions in varying degrees of clarity and intensity that we have acquired in our experience mostly with others." (Gaherao, Youvraj Balaram, 2012)

"Self-concept is how an individual thinks and believe about self, it is the sum of how an individual think and sees the self. It consists of ideas, the way a person feels and the way a person behaved." (Wallang Pahsyntiew, Ayophika, 2021)

According to the above definitions, Self-concept is the image we have of ourselves. The self-concept is a set of attitudes, feelings, and perceptions about oneself that an individual possesses. It is influenced by many forces, including our interaction with important people in our lives. It is how we perceive our behaviors, abilities, and unique characteristics.

Significance of the study

Self –concept signifies the image of an individual. In simple word it can be said that it is a state of awareness about one’s have and haven’t. It also includes the self-confidence of an individual. If a student knows about himself or herself properly, he or she can choose a right path and a better career for future life. Self-concept helps in developing one’s hopes and will power for successful academic and career life. **Kotnal (2020)** revealed that the main effect of self-concept (Low and high) on career aspiration of Unaided Pre-University College Science students was found statistically significant than Govt. and aided Pre-University College Science students. **Ganai (2020)** found that Students from private schools have higher self-concept and career aspirations than students from public schools. Adolescence period is the most important period of life. In this period student tries to find his or her position in family, school, society and so and so. Thoroughly, they identify themselves and know what other people think about them. Senior secondary school students fall under the adolescence period. Therefore, it is essential to examine senior secondary school students' self-concept to develop their personalities and construct a better future.

Review of related Literature

A review of related literature involves collecting and reading relevant journals, books, abstracts, and other reference materials for topic of the study.

Studies related to self-concept

Rais (2008) studied on “Self-concept and level of aspiration: a comparative study of working and non-working mothers’ children”. The objective was to study the self-concept and level of aspiration (Educational and Occupational) of children of working and non-working mothers. And to study the self-concept and level of aspiration (Educational and Occupational) of male and female children. The findings revealed that the level of self-concept of children of working mothers had been found lower in comparison with non-working mothers. Also found that male children possessed bright self-concept than female.

Senthamilselvam S (2017) examined on “Self-concept and Level of Aspiration of Higher Secondary students in relation with their Academic achievement”. The objectives of the

study were i) To study the self-concept of higher secondary students. ii) To analyze the self-concept of higher secondary students with respect to gender, locality of the school, type of the family and subject specification. The result revealed that there was no significant difference between the self-concept and its dimensions of higher secondary students with respect to their gender, locality of the school, types of their family, with their subject specification.

Singh, Preeti (2018) studied on “Academic performance in relation to internet usage peer victimization and self-concept among adolescents”. The objectives were to study the relationship between Peer Victimization and Self –concept, relationship between self-concept and Internet usage and to study the relationship between academic performance and self-concept. The result revealed that peer victimization and self-concept were negatively significantly correlated, self-concept and internet usage were negatively significantly correlated. Self-concept and academic performance were positively significantly correlated.

Yadav, S (2019) studied on “Influence of Values on Self-concept and Adjustment of Higher Secondary School Students”. The objective was to study the significant mean differences of self-concept among higher secondary school students belongs to good, average and poor categories of theoretical dimension of values. It was found that, there was a significant mean difference of self-concept among higher secondary school students belongs to good, average and poor categories of theoretical dimension of values. It means that theoretical dimension of values influences the self-concept of higher secondary school students.

Ganai (2020) carried out a study on “A Study of Self-concept and Career Aspiration among Senior Secondary School Students of Central Kashmir with Reference to Gender and Type of School”. The objective of the study was to study the career aspiration and self-concept of the senior secondary students with reference to gender and type of school. The findings of the study revealed that Students from private schools had higher self-concept and career aspirations than students from public schools. There was no significant difference between

male and female students in self-concept and career aspirations.

S. Pichaipillai (2022) carried out study on “Aspiration Self-concept and Adjustment as The Predictors of Academic Achievement among Higher Secondary School Tribal Students”. The objectives were to find the level of Aspiration, Self-Concept, Adjustment and Academic Achievement among higher secondary school tribal students. Result revealed that there was a significant difference in Self-Concept among higher secondary school tribal students with respect to Gender and types of school. Also revealed that there was no significant difference in Self-Concept among higher secondary school tribal students with respect to parent’s educational qualifications.

Rather, Tawheed Lateef (2023) studied on “Self-concept study habits and emotional intelligence in relation to academic achievement among secondary school students”. The objective was to study the relationship of academic achievement with self-concept, study habits and emotional intelligence of secondary school students with respect to gender, types of school and locality of school. The study revealed that self- concept, study habits, and emotional intelligence, were positively and significantly associated with academic achievement for the entire sample of secondary school students.

Based on the literature reviewed above, it seems reasonable to conclude that most of the studies found no significant difference in self-concept levels between male and female. Another point to consider is that most of the study focused on self-concept among higher secondary students based on gender, school location, parental educational level, and so on. As a result, the researcher encouraged more research into self-concept among 12th-grade senior secondary school students based on gender and management type of school in sivasagar district Assam.

Statement of the Problem

The present study entitled as “Self-Concept of Senior Secondary School Students in relation to their Gender and Types of Management of School in Sivasagar District Assam”.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are –

- I. To study the level of self-concept of senior secondary school students in Sivasagar district Assam.
- II. To analyze whether there is significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to gender.
- III. To analyze whether there is significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to Types of Management of School.

Hypotheses of the study

The hypotheses of the study are-

- I. There is no significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to Gender.
- II. There is no significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to Types of Management of School.

Operational Definitions of the Terms

Self-concept: In the present study Self-concept refers to the set of attitudes, feelings, and perceptions possesses by the secondary school students of Sivasagar districts of Assam. Six dimensions viz. Physical, Social, Temperamental, Educational, Moral and Intellectual will be included in the study.

Senior Secondary School Students: In the present study Senior Secondary School Students refers to those students who are studying in class 12th of senior/higher secondary schools in Sivasagar district of Assam under Assam Higher Secondary Education Council.

Gender: In the present study gender means both male and female students of 12th class.

Types of management: It refers to the Govt. and Private senior Secondary schools recognized by Assam Higher Secondary Education Council. In the present study Govt. schools refer to both the Govt. and Provincialized higher secondary schools.

Delimitations

The delimitations of the study were-

The study was delimited to senior secondary schools both govt. & private recognized by Assam Higher Secondary Education Council.

The result of the study will be applicable for Sivasagar district only

Methodology and procedure

Method used

The present study employed the descriptive survey method.

Population

The population of the present study comprises the 12th class senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam.

Sample

The investigator used stratified random sampling technique for selecting 100 samples (male 50 and female 50) of 12th class senior secondary school students. The samples were selected through giving weightage on gender (male & female) and types of management of school (govt. & private) from two schools of sivasagar district Assam.

Tools used

The investigator used personnel data sheet developed by herself and Self-Concept Questionnaire by Dr. R.K. Saraswat (2024). The questionnaire consists of 48 items. It provides six separate dimensions of self-concept - physical, social, temperamental, educational, moral, and intellectual. The reliability of Self-concept questionnaire is 0.91 and this indicates as a reliable measure of self –concept responses.

Procedure of data collection

For the present study data were collected by the investigator. Each participant provided informed consent with strict assurance of anonymity. Prior to administering the research instrument, the investigator provided a comprehensive explanation regarding the study's objectives and the preferred method of response. Furthermore, participants were guaranteed that all data collected would be treated with utmost confidentiality and solely utilized for research purpose.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

After collecting the data, the investigator scored the data, which was analyzed using percentage, mean, SD and a t-test was used to find the difference between male & female and govt. & private school students.

Interpretation of results has given below-

Objective I: To study the level of Self-Concept of Senior Secondary school students in Sivasagar district Assam.

Table-1 Level of self-concept of senior secondary school students in Sivasagar district Assam

Sl. No	Level of Self-concept	Row Scores	No. of Students	% of Students
1	High Self-Concept	193 to 240	03	3%
2	Above Average Self-Concept	145 to 192	93	93%
3	Average Self-concept	97 to 144	04	4%
4	Below Average Self-concept	49 to 96	Nil	Nil
5	Low Self-Concept	1 to 48	Nil	Nil
	Total Sample		100	100%

Figure-1 Self-concept among Senior Secondary School Students

Table 1 & the figure 1: Indicates that out of 100 sample 3% students have high level of self-concept, 93% students have above average level of self-concept, and 4% students have average level of self-concept. There are no

respondents who have below average self-concept and low level of self-concept

Therefore, it may be interpreted that the majority of the senior secondary school students of sivasagar district have an above average level of self-concept.

Objective 2: To analyze whether there is significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to gender.

Hypothesis Testing I: There is no significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to gender.

Table-2 Comparison of self-concept level of senior secondary school students in Sivasagar district Assam with respect to gender.

Gender	Male	Female
No. Students	50	50
Mean	165.20	165.28
SD	12.16	10.96
Degrees of Freedom	98	
t value	0.97	
Level of significance	Not significant at 0.05 level of significance	

It is evident that the calculated value of “t” for comparing self-concept among male and female students was found 0.97 which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance for two tailed tests for degree of freedom (df)=98, because the calculated “t” value (0.97) is less than the table “t” value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis “there is no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students” is accepted. This indicates that the observed difference between the two means is not statistically significant.

Therefore, it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference in the mean score of self-concept among male and female

senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam. So, the findings of the study reveal that both male and female students of senior secondary schools exhibit more or less same level of self-concept. This finding is consonance with the findings of Lalchhanchhuahi & Fanai (2022), S. Anantha Babu and Dr. K. Krishnamoorthy (2016), Ganai (2020) which stated that there is no significant difference in the level of self-concept among higher secondary school students in relation to their gender.

Objective 3: To analyze whether there is significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to Types of Management of School.

Hypothesis Testing II: There is no significant difference in self-concept of senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam in relation to Types of Management of School.

Table-3 Comparison of self-concept level of senior secondary school students in Sivasagar district Assam in relation to types of management of school

Gender	Male	Private
No. Students	50	50
Mean	162.9	167.58
SD	8.59	13.53
Degrees of Freedom	98	
t value	0.04	
Level of significance	Not significant at 0.05 level of significance	

It is evident that the calculated value of “t” for comparing self-concept among govt. and private senior secondary school students was found 0.04 which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance for two tailed tests for degree of freedom (df)=98, because the calculated “t” value (0.04) is less than the table “t” value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis “there is no significant difference

between govt. and private senior secondary school students” is accepted. This indicates that the observed difference between the two means is not statistically significant.

Therefore, it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference in the mean score of self-concept among govt. and private senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam. So, the findings of the study reveal that both govt. and private senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district exhibit more or less same level of self-concept.

Discussion

The overall study with regard to self-concept shows that majority of senior secondary school students in sivasagar district, Assam have above average level of self-concept. This finding is in line with the findings of Christina Lalchhanchhuahi & Prof. Lallianzuali Fanai (2022) who found that majority of the students possess above average self-concept. The present study also found that the mean score of female self-concept is higher than male students. This finding is in line with the findings of Lalchhanchhuahi & Fanai (2022), S. Anantha Babu and Dr. K. Krishnamoorthy (2016), Ganai (2020) who found that female students reported to have a better Self-concept than male students. However, the calculated t-value is less than the table value at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

From the study it is also revealed that the mean score of private senior secondary school students’ self-conception is higher than the govt. senior secondary school students’ self-conception is higher than the government. The calculated t-value is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it may be interpreted that there is no significant difference in the mean score of self-concept among govt. and private senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam.

Recommendation for Further Research:

Based on the result of the present study some recommendations can be made for further study. The recommendations are as follows-

- I. The study can be expanded to additional districts or states.
- II. Study can be expanded by including more variables related to self-concept.
- III. Can conduct comparative study based on locality, school environment, family environment, educational status of parents etc.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis and interpretation of the data presented above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Out of 100 sample 3% students have a high level of self-concept, 93% of students have above average level of self-concept and 4% students have average level of self-concept.
- There is no significant difference in the mean score of self-concept among male and female senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam. Both male and female senior secondary school students possess same level of self-concept. Mean score of male students is 165.20 which is lower than the mean score of female students which is 165.28.
- There is no significant difference in the mean score of self-concept among govt. and private senior secondary school students of Sivasagar district Assam. Both govt. and private senior secondary school students possess the same level of self-concept. Mean score of govt. senior secondary school is 162.9 which is lower than the mean score of private school which is 167.58.

The reason behind this result may be due to the diverse family background, educational environment in school, parental involvement of students in academic as well as other factors of life. Also, adolescence is the period where children face a lot of changes in their physical and mental life. Therefore, their level of self-concept is more or less from each group.

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